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CONSOLIDATION OF THE ROLE OF CORPORATE STRUCTURES' INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT

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The authors consider modern tendencies of innovative activity development in corporate structures under conditions of competitive environment. The most common scenarios of the creation of companies' innovative development structure taking into account the features of their innovative activity organization and substantiation of imperfection reasons are investigated.

Use of the marketing component in the system of corporate structures' innovative development as an important factor in meeting perspective needs of the consumer and the factor of market opportunities expansion for innovative development of corporate structures is emphasized.

Recommendations on the development of innovations marketing in corporate structures that envisage market opportunities of innovative development consolidation are proposed. Expediency of the relationship between marketing research concerning the choice of new products during the interaction of all participants in the innovation process is discovered.

Keywords: innovations, marketing, innovative activity, innovations marketing, corporate structure.

ПОСИЛЕННЯ РОЛІ ІННОВАЦІЙНОГО РОЗВИТКУ КОРПОРАТИВНИХ СТРУКТУР

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Розглянуто сучасні тенденції розвитку інноваційної діяльності в корпоративних структурах в умовах конкурентного середовища. Досліджено найбільш поширені сценарії створення структури інноваційного розвитку

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компаній з урахуванням особливостей організації їх інноваційної діяльності та обґрунтування причин недосконалості.

Акцентовано увагу на застосуванні маркетингової складової в системі інноваційного розвитку корпоративних структур як важливому факторі задоволення перспективних потреб споживача та чинника розширення ринкових можливостей інноваційного розвитку корпоративних структур.

Запропоновано рекомендації щодо розвитку маркетингу інновацій в корпоративних структурах, які передбачають посилення ринкових можливостей інноваційного розвитку. Розкрито доцільність взаємозв'язку маркетингового пошуку щодо вибору нових продуктів у ході взаємодії всіх учасників інноваційного процесу.

Ключові слова: інновації, маркетинг, інноваційна діяльність, маркетинг інновацій, корпоративна структура.

УСИЛЕНИЕ РОЛИ ИННОВАЦИОННОГО РАЗВИТИЯ КОРПОРАТИВНЫХ СТРУКТУР

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Рассмотрены современные тенденции развития инновационной деятельности в корпоративных структурах в условиях конкурентной среды. Исследованы наиболее распространенные сценарии создания структуры инновационного развития компаний с учетом особенностей организации их инновационной деятельности и объяснения причин несовершенства.

Акцентировано внимание на применении маркетинга в системе инновационного развития корпоративных структур как важной составляющей удовлетворения перспективных потребностей потребителей и фактора расширения рыночных возможностей инновационного развития корпоративных структур.

Предложены рекомендации по развитию маркетинга инноваций в корпоративных структурах, предусматривающие усиление рыночных возможностей инновационного развития. Раскрыто целесообразность взаимосвязи маркетингового поиска по выбору новых продуктов в ходе взаимодействия всех участников инновационного процесса.

Ключевые слова: инновации, маркетинг, инновационная деятельность, маркетинг инноваций, корпоративная структура.

Statement of the problem. Today, competitiveness of national economy of any country directly depends on the pace of its development. At the same time, the pledge of national economy accelerated development is scientific and technological progress, which is impossible to imagine without its innovative component. Therefore, the role of innovative development, as a leading factor of growth, assumes prominence.

Corporate structures, which assume the main function of realizing the state policy concerning the transition to an innovative way of

development nowadays, play a special role in solving this problem. The activity of corporate structures aimed at the development and use of the results of scientific research that enables to ensure profitability of the activity by meeting the current market needs, today, can safely be called one of the most effective directions for ensuring the increase of production efficiency. However, at the same time, there is a complex problem of market «support» of innovations, development and commercialization of new goods and services.

Therefore, research of the problems concerning development and implementation of innovative activity by corporate structures not only through the generation of scientific research and development, but also for the purpose of their further commercialization and through the introduction of effective mechanisms for innovative activity management, is relevant.

Review of the latest research and publications. Issues of innovative development and interaction between innovative process participants have been studied by such scholars as B. Ludnval, V. Geets, P. Drucker, K. Prakhlad, H. Hemel, H. Chesbro, H. Itskovich, A. Kuzmin, R. Nelson, I. Pavlenko, M. Porter, B. Santo, S. Sokolenko, V. Solovyov, B. Twis, L. Fedulova, K. Freeman, F. Khayek, J. Schumpeter, G. Chesbrough, N. Chukhraj and many other scholars. Particular attention to marketing of innovations and activity of modern flexible and mobile innovative structures has been paid by such scientists as S. Blank, A. Zozuliov, V. Ilchuk, E. Ris, K.M. Khristensen and P. Tsybuliov. They have studied various aspects of innovative activity and forms of interaction between its participants in the processes of RED and commercialization of new products. However, despite of this, a wide range of methodological and methodic issues concerning the place of marketing in the system of corporate structures' innovative development remains open.

The objective of the research. The purpose of the paper is to substantiate the appropriateness of cross-functional interaction in corporate structures in the direction of generating innovative ideas, their timely perception by entrepreneurs and creating conditions for their rapid commercialization.

Presentation of the research material. There are many obstacles on the way to the development of innovative activity – some of them are related with application and implementation of the idea, the others are «stuck» in the organization's ideas about «what innovative activity is» and “what can be achieved with its help”. As a result, most companies have a lack of top management and employees support within the company on the way to innovation; lack of trust and lack of experience in the field of changes implementation; lack of common goals and obligations; lack of innovation culture; lack of resources for innovative activity; loss of control

over the organization of processes; fear of unknown and uncontrolled processes; critical attitude on the part of partners; lack of remuneration and motivation system; lack of general understanding of the essence of innovation for the organization; lack of any practical system of quick assessment to the results of innovative activity; lack of collaboration and information exchange between the developer team and other departments – the marketing, supply, quality control, regulation and finance departments; lack of creative knowledge, knowledge in competitive intelligence and comparative analysis of technologies, etc.

That is, innovative activity of the enterprise needs to be developed in the system of already established interconnection with all market participants, including participants of the corporate environment, which will promote effective marketing of innovations and stable functioning of the company in the market. In addition, the communication process should be double-sided: on the one hand, the company should strive to influence the target and other audiences, and on the other hand, to receive contrary information about the response of these audiences to its action [1].

Modern world practice of implementing innovations within the companies shows that there are several scenarios for the development:

1) rejection of innovations. Realizing the ever-increasing competition on the market, and within the framework of its existing structure, the company does not have the capacity to create innovative solutions;

2) creation of conditions for innovation. The company has the opportunity to innovate, but there is no proper environment and structure for innovations implementation;

3) adaptation of the company's business model to innovations. Business model of the company begins losing its relevance, and therefore it is decided to separate the direction of innovation activity from the operating system and to develop a new concept for it;

4) search for new opportunities for innovation, development of new products. The company is looking for opportunities to maintain and grow its position in the market by increasing speed and cheapening the processes of introducing new technologies and developing new products.

All of these scenarios, on the one hand, are prerequisites for organizing innovative activity within the company, and on the other hand, explain the risks of its «not organization». This happens primarily due to the specificity of the innovation itself. Firstly, it associates with a high probability of errors and failures, and in most cases, innovation cannot guarantee the expected instantaneous result, and secondly, employees can create any innovative solution within the company, that is, to feel the right corporate momentum to develop new ideas, but implement it outside the company.

Such circumstances explain the low level of companies (about 5%), which feel confident and comfortable at their markets, and in terms of innovations, they have already created a «complete set of tools» for working with the market of innovations:

- flexible and dynamic internal culture and high salaries, attracting the best personnel;
- infrastructure, own and affiliate, where they carry out innovative actions and work;
- corporate funds that purchase startups with an enviable regularity;
- own acceleration programs for filtering and integrating startups and their technologies.

They are mainly concerned with the improvement of their internal ecosystem and enrichment of the innovation environment around them.

They also often provide free activities for the community, grant open access to some of their works, and support research in various areas of applied science.

More mature in terms of readiness for innovation are those Ukrainian and foreign companies (now there is not more than 15% of such companies in the world), which have the first necessary tools for work with innovations, as well as experience. For example, in launching their own accelerators at the Ukrainian market, in organizing own venture funds and in building their own innovative infrastructure. Many of the aforementioned companies have elements of innovative culture in the form of innovation departments, training of top managers for tools that allow more flexible project management and understanding customer needs.

80% of companies with a stable business provide basic needs with standard market practices, understanding the importance of innovation, but are generally not prepared to devote significant resources to any changes and are not interested in additional risks and, consequently, in rapid changes. These companies do not have effective corporate innovative tools, and they are not ready to spend substantial funds for their implementation, because innovation is primarily an investment in the future.

According to the Law of Ukraine «On Innovative Activity», innovations are newly created or improved competitive technologies, products or services, as well as organizational and technical decisions of an industrial, administrative, commercial or other nature. They significantly improve the structure and quality of production and social sphere; innovative activity is an activity aimed at the use and commercialization of research results and development, promotes the launch of new competitive products, and services [2].

Every company that seeks to dynamically develop in the market, requires innovations, and hence – an effective concept of the company's market activity (business philosophy), when the source of income is seen in changes, that is, «marketing of innovations».

Today, there is no consensus on how the categories of «marketing» and «innovation» are combined. There is also no common definition of «innovative marketing» and «marketing of innovations». Marketing of innovations is viewed as an analytical process that involves identification of market opportunities for innovation development; as a way of active influence on consumers and the target market as a whole, connected with the output and promotion of innovations on the market; as a function of innovation management, aimed at the identification of possible areas of innovation activity, their materialization and commercialization. «At the same time, one can simultaneously consider innovative management as a function of marketing of innovations, aimed at realizing the achievements of science and technology in new products, able to satisfy needs and demands of consumers and to provide profit for commodity producer (seller); as a tool (market toolkit) orientation of individual economic entities, and, at the same time, the whole national economy on innovation development»[3].

While introducing innovations into the practice of marketing activities, it is advisable to determine what factors can slow down or speed up the innovation process. At the same time, special attention should be paid to the human factor. Innovation introduces changes in the existing solutions. On the part of employees, there exists inevitable resistance to changes that can cause such effects as change in the status of employees, the need for a job search, reorganization of work and steady ways of doing business, violations of the stereotypes of behavior and traditions, uncertainty, fear of punishment for failure. For people affected by these changes, this means breaking their traditional position, so the function of motivation for innovations becomes meaningful [4].

The number of subjects of corporate relations, the presence of not only common but also different interests inside them, indicates a certain system of interests, which reflects the connections and dependencies between them. This system involves the presence of a rod, which is designed to ensure its functioning as a single whole. Corporate interest is considered to be such a rod. Considering the priority of certain types of interests – personal, collective, public or social - in corporation, it should be borne in mind that such species do not exist in pure form and their provision is possible only if the balance is established and maintained between them [5].

Under such circumstances, it is about creating an effective corporate innovation marketing system within the company, which should be a tool for strategic development of the company through the promotion of

innovation and change management, and to exist as a corporate culture - from the moment the company emerges and to the very end.

Innovation development implies a radical change in approach to staff development. The company, opened to innovations, transforms approaches to recruitment, approves the exit of employees beyond the scope of official duties in finding solutions for problems, encourages internal informal groups, and provides direct and open communication with management staff [6].

The company demonstrates its course on organizing innovative activities for the market and employees through particular actions and statements of internal leaders and top management. These actions may include identification of innovation as a key component of a business strategy, identification of the focus and objectives of innovation, assigning and defining personal responsibility for internal sponsors and managers, identification of motivation programs, and allocation of other resources to support innovation as strategic initiatives.

The innovator company builds a strategy for interacting with the outside world, focusing not only on solving current tactical business tasks, it also uses external connections to find and implement promising solutions, attract the best people and change the reputation in the market.

Now new ideas and technologies are rapidly emerging in the market, changing the way of doing business, destroying old markets and creating new ones in months, completely changing the landscape of the economy. Innovative companies are ready for quick understanding, adoption and adaptation of the new rules of the game, perceiving subversive technologies as an opportunity for success, but not a threat to business.

It is advisable to create a staff team of personnel engaged in strategy development, management of innovation programs and their activation within the company [7]. The participants of the innovation group are simultaneously experts on internal corporate communications and sources of change. Such programs are centered within the company and can include full-time and part-time employees working on the strategy and control of innovation programs. However, experts of such teams should be selected very carefully – they must have experience in communicating with other units and be able to influence the position of the entire company. Innovations, which are the main source of competitive advantages, determine the success of each leading company in virtually any industry. Today they are so easily copied that the basis of the leadership strategy in this area is not even access to technology, but an ability of firms to bring their technological potential in line with market requirements.

Under such conditions, the cooperation of profile innovation marketing teams with traditional R & D divisions and operational departments is effective, which in fact proves the world practice of innovation activity.

Such corporate balance of power, on the one hand, allows avoiding the development of technologically complex products, which are not able to put a new direction in the development of consumer demand, and therefore fail in the market. On the other hand, it helps to avoid a situation where emphasized attention to market requirements without proper understanding of technological opportunities leads to extensive, rather than intensive development of the existing products. In this case, firms cannot get a significant increase in opportunities for innovation.

In order to avoid the launch of very complicated proposals, but at the same time to create revolutionary products meeting market requirements, throughout the innovation process (from the original idea to launching the product on the market), companies must effectively combine the work of two business units: the direction of new developments (R & D) and marketing.

If the work of these services is interconnected, and their information systems are integrated, they have a common vision of the innovation project. There is mutual trust, open information exchange. They often interact; mutually provide data and use information together to make decisions, for example, concerning the benefits of the product. This prevents the domination of one functional department over another, which threatens to eliminate unclaimed innovations (when a new development department has a pre-marketing advantage) or launching another «reincarnation» of the existing product (if marketing manages the work of engineers).

Involving people from R & D and marketing into one cross-functional team within the framework of matrix approach contributes to a significant increase in integration between the divisions. In this regard, it is interesting to note that one of the first initiatives of the newly appointed CEO of Opel was the introduction of cross-functional teams to increase integration and, consequently, reduce the time to market products, as well as to improve their quality development.

A special option for R & D and marketing integration operates in the American company Maytag, which ranks third place in the United States for the manufacture of large household appliances (and has recently joined Whirlpool). Both functions are carried out by the Advanced Innovation in Technology division, the tasks of which are formulated in two ways: on the one hand, it must engage in the study and forecasting of the needs of consumers, on the other – the study of the latest technologies that help bring about new ideas.

To solve the first task, the service of consumer market monitoring is provided in the structure of the department (in terms of internal structure, it is divided into divisions; each of them is responsible for the development of a particular product line). With its help, Maytag watches how the lifestyle of

a typical modern family changes. Full occupancy of family members makes people cook and eat outside home more often. However, they still have an internal desire to make the family's food balanced. In view of this, the department of advanced technological innovation, as part of its strategic task, is considering different ways for creating such a medium for consumers in which they can cook easily and quickly.

The Department of Advanced Technology Innovations is managed by the Chief Technology Officer, to whom two directors report. The department also has project managers and full-time engineers. The main responsibility for a major project relies on one of the project managers who manages a cross-functional team of engineers.

Such teams do not just turn the desire and the needs of customers into the language of technology – they do this, combining the capabilities of specialists with various knowledge. For example, when working on the creation of a corner furnace for kitchen furniture (a new product concept), engineers from the Advanced Innovation Technology Division collaborate with engineers responsible for ovens development to create a conversion / convection oven, while at the same time it is possible to place it next to the TV. Problems of this kind have never arisen before, as the company Maytag was engaged only in the development of constructively independent devices. Now, when they become relevant, their solution requires integration not only between marketing and development, but also within the service itself. That is, creating an effective mechanism for corporate marketing of innovation, which is a manifestation of corporate culture of the company, supports innovation and emphasizes their importance as an instrument of new developments and marketing integration.

Table 1

Areas of innovations marketing development in corporate structures

Directions	Essence and implementation
1	2
Strategy and direction	Innovative activity is considered one of the main factors of business increase and transformation. Assessment of innovative development level is made and steps concerning its improvement are developed: organization of internal processes, innovation culture, research of innovation development strategy and key performance indicators

Continuation of table

1	2
Integration of processes	Search of startups, teams, products and technologies on Ukrainian and international markets according to the request of the company with further integration. Formulation of internal request for innovation by business divisions of the company, and implementation of the entire list of procedures for the formation of projects short lists, and integration of startups: formulation of the request for innovation within the organization, creation of a funnel of projects based on the criteria of the request, systematization and selection of projects, creation of perspective projects' short lists, piloting startups, integration of startups into the company structure. The process of finding innovations is funded in a sufficient amount
Culture and people	Implementation of an effective innovation support environment, processes directed to attracting staff and promptly making key decisions. Each employee has the opportunity to participate in the process of innovations implementing, the Institute of mentoring from more experienced employees is organized. Innovation is a key topic for top management
Organizational development	Internal teams on innovations have been organized. Funding is provided for the involvement of external experts, implementation of advanced technologies and the prototyping of perspective hypotheses. Conducting a thorough business analysis to identify bottlenecks and potential areas, where new technologies can be applied. Compilation of all reliable sources of innovation and innovative ideas in selected areas. Weekly / monthly reviews and selection of the most important events and examples of innovations application in the relevant area. Estimation of potential impact of each event or technology on the company, its activities and target markets. Identifying opportunities for investment and growth, as well as potential threats to business. Development of recommendations for responding to positive and negative effects that provides new technologies for each business

Continuation of table

1	2
Openness to external influences	The process of introducing innovations involves working with contractors, suppliers, and educational institutions. Expert communities are formed, crowdsourcing of ideas is applied. Work of training centers is organized that helps employees and top management to master the skills and methodologies of innovative thinking and innovation development in the company, aimed at both subversive innovations as well as support and optimization approaches. Additional obtaining by staff of the required competencies in the following areas: Intellectual Property, Innovative Project Management, Risk Management Methodologies in Innovation Projects at All Stages of Development, Personal Skills and Development of Business Competencies, Marketing of Innovative Products, Investments and Legal Issues of Investing
Readiness for rapid changes	An internal innovation team constantly monitors current trends, assesses the potential for their application, and informs relevant colleagues about successful practices and perspectives. Different techniques are actively used: experiments, creation of innovation incubators, use of open innovation, innovative outposts, venture funds, etc

Common understanding and vision of innovation importance creates the need for cross-functional collaboration in the genetic structure of the organization. This motivates and allows employees to strive for establishing effective communication – formal and informal – with colleagues from other departments that contribute to the overall vision.

We suggest developing the marketing of innovations in corporate structures in the following areas:

- strategy and direction;
- integration of processes;
- culture and people;
- organizational development;
- openness to external influences;
- readiness for rapid changes (Table 1).

Conclusions. Consequently, effective innovative development in corporate structures primarily involves creation of effective culture of entrepreneurship within the company for the sake of innovation, which can

act as a separate product, be an innovation marketing technology, and be the result of other types of innovations. The leading role in this case is given to marketing services, which are the participants of the company innovation group and are in close interaction with other company services for the formation of mentality aimed at innovations, improvement of innovative processes, and creation of consumer value, increase of income and preservation of its competitive advantages among employees.

Establishing interconnection of the effective forms of marketing research concerning the choice of new products in the process of interaction between innovation process participants using modern tools of innovation marketing is necessary to meet the growing consumer requirements to the quality of offered goods and services and their successful promotion.

Creating a modern innovation base in corporate structures, promoting their innovation activities through the introduction of economic mechanism to support promising innovative ideas and application of effective business models of strategic development is the key to their transition to the innovative model of effective development.

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СУЧАСНІ ПРОБЛЕМИ ЯКОСТІ ТРУДОВОГО ЖИТТЯ НАСЕЛЕННЯ УКРАЇНИ

Н.І. Єсінова

Досліджено сучасні проблеми та методи покращення якості трудового життя населення, їх вплив на поведінку робітників. Охарактеризована роль організації праці на підприємстві. Проведено аналіз якості трудового життя в Україні. Проаналізовано важливість високого рівня якості трудового життя для розвитку підприємства зокрема і держави загалом. Визначено основні недоліки в сучасній організації праці України. Установлено, що висока якість трудового життя веде підприємство до успіху, що продемонстровано на прикладах найуспішніших компаній світу.

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